

Crafting confidence, designing smiles with veneers: A case-based esthetic journey.

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Abstract

Anterior diastema and aesthetic discrepancies in tooth form and shade can significantly affect a patient's smile, confidence, and psychosocial well-being. A multidisciplinary and minimally invasive approach is often required to restore optimal function and smile harmony. Porcelain veneers and all-ceramic crowns, especially those fabricated from lithium disilicate and zirconia, offer an effective treatment modality in such scenarios. This article presents two clinical cases: the first involving generalized diastema managed with maxillary veneers and mandibular crowns, and the second addressing mottled and undersized anterior teeth using lithium disilicate veneers. Both treatments resulted in excellent functional and esthetic outcomes with high patient satisfaction and stable soft tissue response.

Keywords: Anterior esthetics, diastema, lithium disilicate, porcelain veneers, smile rehabilitation, zirconia crowns.

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Introduction

Diastema, defined as spacing between adjacent teeth, most commonly affects the maxillary anterior segment and can arise from multiple etiological factors including genetics, abnormal frenum attachment, tooth-size arch-length discrepancies, habits (e.g., tongue thrust), and periodontal disease.^[1]

While orthodontic and surgical interventions may be indicated in certain cases, fixed prosthetic solutions offer immediate and predictable esthetic improvements, particularly in adult patients unwilling to undergo prolonged orthodontic therapy.^[2]

Lithium disilicate ceramics have gained popularity for anterior restorations due to their favorable optical characteristics, high flexural strength (360–400 MPa), and excellent enamel bonding potential.^[3,4] When enamel is preserved during preparation, bonding protocols yield superior retention and longevity.^[5,6] In contrast, full-

coverage all-ceramic crowns are indicated when teeth exhibit discoloration, wear, or structural compromise.^[7] The integration of digital smile design, mock-ups, and adhesive protocols enables clinicians to deliver highly personalized and natural-looking outcomes.^[8]

This paper presents two case reports utilizing a combination of veneers and crowns to address anterior diastema and esthetic anomalies.

Case Report 1: Diastema Management with Maxillary Veneers and Mandibular Crowns

Patient Information

A 27-year-old female presented with generalized spacing between her upper and lower anterior teeth. She expressed concern over the esthetic appearance and desired a long-lasting, fixed, and esthetically pleasing solution (Figure 1).

Clinical Findings

Intraoral examination revealed multiple diastema involving teeth #13–#23 and #33–#43. All teeth were well-aligned with healthy periodontal tissues. Maxillary and mandibular teeth exhibited adequate enamel thickness. Occlusion was stable with no evidence of parafunction (Figure 2).

Treatment Procedure

Diagnostic Phase:

Preoperative records were collected, including intraoral photographs and diagnostic impressions. A wax-up was fabricated to guide tooth preparation and visualize diastema closure. A bis-acryl mock-up was placed intraorally to assess esthetic outcomes and confirm patient expectations. Shade matching was performed under natural daylight using the VITA 3D Master guide. The same value was selected for both veneers and crowns to maintain uniformity.

Tooth Preparation:

Maxillary Veneers: 0.5–0.7 mm labial reduction and 1.5 mm incisal edge reduction with a chamfer finish line. Mandibular Crowns: Axial reduction of 1.0 mm and incisal reduction of 1.5 mm with a shoulder finish line.

Impression and Temporization:

Final impressions were taken using a two-step putty-wash technique with polyvinyl siloxane (PVS). Gingival retraction was achieved with 3M Astringent Retraction Paste. Bis-acrylic resin temporaries (Structur 3, VOCO) were fabricated and cemented (Figure 3).

Veneer Try-In:

Lithium disilicate veneers were tried in using try-in paste. The patient approved the shade,

shape, and surface texture. Margins were verified clinically and radiographically.

Cementation:

The intaglio surfaces of the veneers and crowns were etched with 9% hydrofluoric acid for 20 seconds, followed by rinsing and drying. A silane coupling agent was applied for enhanced bonding. On the tooth surfaces, 37% phosphoric acid etching was done for 15 seconds, rinsed, and followed by bonding agent application. Dual-cure resin cement (Calibra Veneer) was used to seat the veneers & crowns, and excess was carefully removed before polymerization. Each veneer and crown was light-cured for 40 seconds from multiple angles, followed by occlusal adjustments and polishing (Figure 4).

Outcome:

All diastemata were effectively closed, and an esthetic, symmetrical smile was achieved. At one-month follow-up, restorations remained intact, and soft tissues exhibited excellent response. The patient expressed high satisfaction with phonetics and appearance.

Case Report 2: Aesthetic Management of Small and Mottled Anterior Teeth

Patient Information:

A 34-year-old male patient reported dissatisfaction with the size and mottled appearance of his upper front teeth. He requested a conservative solution that would enhance his smile (Figure 5).

Clinical Findings:

Maxillary central, lateral incisors and canine were shorter than average and displayed white enamel flecks and irregularities. There were no signs of active caries or periodontal disease. Various treatment options were

presented to the patient, and the use of ceramic veneers was recommended based on the clinical findings and the patient's aesthetic concerns. Given that ceramic veneers are primarily elective and esthetic in nature, a thorough discussion was conducted outlining the benefits, potential risks, and detailed steps involved in the procedure to ensure informed consent and realistic expectations.

Diagnostic Phase:

Shade matching was done using the Vita 3D Classical shade guide. Diagnostic impressions were made, and a wax-up was performed to idealize tooth proportions.

Mock-Up:

An intraoral mock-up was performed using a silicone index to transfer the wax-up into the mouth with bis-acrylic material.

The patient approved the new proportions and contour (Figure 6).

Tooth Preparation:

A well-adapted, sectioned silicon matrix was made from the diagnostic cast, which was later used as a reference for teeth reduction. Labial reduction of 0.5–0.7 mm and incisal reduction of approximately 1.0–1.5 mm was carried out. A fine chamfer margin was placed with all line angles rounded. Care was taken to stay within enamel for optimal bond strength (Figure 7).

Final Impression:

Retraction paste (3M Astringent Retraction Paste) were placed, and a final impression was taken using a two-stage putty-wash PVS technique. Shade and stump shade were recorded for laboratory communication.

Provisionalization:

Provisional veneers were fabricated and adjusted for aesthetics and phonetics.

Temporaries were cemented with a non-eugenol cement.

Veneer Try-In:

Lithium disilicate veneers were tried in using try-in paste.

The patient approved the shade, shape, and surface texture.

Margins were verified clinically and radiographically.

Cementation:

Veneers were cleaned and silanated after hydrofluoric acid etching.

Teeth were etched, rinsed, and bonding agent applied. Resin cement was used to bond the veneers under isolation. Excess cement was removed and final curing was done with glycerin gel to ensure complete polymerization (Figure 8).

Follow-Up:

At the one-week follow-up, excellent gingival adaptation and colour stability were observed. The patient reported enhanced self-esteem and satisfaction with her new smile.

Discussion:

Porcelain veneers offer a conservative, esthetic, and predictable solution for anterior dental rehabilitation. In these cases, lithium disilicate ceramics were selected for their superior translucency, high flexural strength, and excellent bonding properties.^[8,10] Their ability to closely mimic natural tooth enamel made them the ideal material for managing esthetic concerns such as discoloration, enamel defects, and size discrepancies.^[3,9]

A systematic approach—including diagnostic wax-up, intraoral mock-up, conservative preparation, and adhesive cementation—was essential for achieving clinical success and patient satisfaction.^[1,2,5]

Special emphasis was placed on preserving enamel during preparation, as bonding to enamel offers significantly higher longevity and strength compared to dentin bonding.^[6,7]

Accurate shade matching, the use of digital tools for smile design, and precise

cementation techniques contributed to lifelike esthetics and long-term predictability.^[2,4,10] Soft tissue health was maintained by adhering to supragingival margins and atraumatic finishing lines.^[5,9] These outcomes align with long-term clinical studies demonstrating high survival and success rates of lithium disilicate veneers, particularly when bonded to enamel and when proper adhesive protocols are followed.^[7,8]

Conclusion:

This case series demonstrates the versatility and reliability of lithium disilicate veneers in addressing diverse esthetic challenges in the anterior region. Through meticulous planning, conservative preparation, and adherence to adhesive protocols, highly satisfactory esthetic and functional outcomes were achieved with minimal biological compromise. Porcelain veneers, particularly lithium disilicate-based restorations, offer a durable, biocompatible, and patient-friendly option for anterior smile rehabilitation. With proper case selection and a systematic clinical approach, long-term success and patient satisfaction can be predictably achieved.

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FIGURES

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Figure 3

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